

DISORDERS OF CALCIUM-PHOSPHORUS METABOLISM IN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS

Kamalova Lobar Yagmurovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384200>

Resume. Among the diseases that cause kidney failure in young children, pyelonephritis takes the first place. Pyelonephritis is a non-specific, mainly infectious and inflammatory process that occurs in the pyelocaliceal system of the kidney and its tubulo-interstitial zone.

Kay words: chronic pyelonephritis, hemostatic, reabsorption, proximal canallar, phosphorus-calcium.

The state of the body is formed by various factors of the internal and external environment, among which the state of calcium-phosphorus metabolism occupies an important place. Disorders of the structure and function of organs involved in the regulation of phosphorus-calcium metabolism are the cause of various diseases that develop during the child's life. Kidneys are the main organ in regulating phosphorus-calcium homeostasis in both physiological and pathological conditions. The main physiological function of the kidneys is to maintain the homeostatic parameters of the body. When primary urine is formed in the vascular glomerulus, it includes all trace elements of blood plasma. Active reabsorption of minerals and water begins in the proximal tubules. Absorption of monovalent cations in the initial part of the tubules is an active process, and in the last part of the tubules - active and passive. Absorption of divalent cations is an active process. Anions passively follow cations. 10-20% of the filtered cations are absorbed in the distal tubules. The reabsorption process of microelements is under the control of the nervous and endocrine systems. When tubules are damaged, the active and passive reabsorption of trace elements from primary urine is disturbed, which leads to a decrease in their content in the body. On the other hand, a deformed mineral metabolism contributes to the pathogenesis of kidney diseases and creates a special "circle". A number of authors have conducted studies that revealed that the composition of elements such as magnesium, zinc, copper, and iron was disturbed in the body of children with chronic pyelonephritis. Cases such as the killing of microorganisms, a steady decrease in immunity were noted. Disorders of magnesium metabolism in children with chronic pyelonephritis are characterized by a decrease in its level in hair and blood serum. One of the causes of magnesium deficiency detected in children with pathological process localization in the tubulointerstitial tissues of the kidneys is the increased excretion of this macroelement through the kidneys. The ability of the kidney to perform homeostatic functions determines the main role of this organ in the processes of bone resorption and bone formation, as well as in the mineralization of teeth.

In pyelonephritis in children, the defeat of the tubulo-interstitial apparatus is accompanied by changes in the state of phosphorus-calcium metabolism. According to A.A. Baranova A.A. (2015), in children aged 8 months to 14 years with a diagnosis of "Chronic pyelonephritis", the concentration of calcium in blood serum is reduced in 77.78% of children with primary pyelonephritis and 78.95% of children with secondary pyelonephritis. A decrease in phosphorus levels was found in 77.78% of children with primary pyelonephritis and 31.58% of children with secondary pyelonephritis. These disorders are characterized by

reabsorption disorders in children with microbial-inflammatory diseases of the kidneys.
билан оғриган бемор болаларда реабсорбциянинг бузилиши билан тавсифланади.

References:

1. Yagmurovna K. L. Digestion in the Mouth and Stomach in the Early Postnatal Period //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2023. – Т. 20. – С. 68-72.
2. Kamalova L. METABOLISM AND ENERGY //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 267-274.
3. Kamalova L. MAIN TYPES OF DIGESTION AND THEIR DISTRIBUTION AMONG GROUPS OF LIVING ORGANISMS //International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 61-66.
4. Камалова Л. СУРУНКАЛИ ПИЕЛОНЕФРИТ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН БЕМОР БОЛАЛАРДА ЎТКАЗИЛГАН СТОМАТОЛОГИК КЛИНИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 13. – С. 258-262
5. Yagmurovna K. L. Disorders of Calcium-Phosphorus Metabolism in Children with Chronic Pyelonephritis //Texas Journal of Medical Science. – 2022. – Т. 14. – С. 80-83.

